

DEVELOPMENT OF TOOLS TO IMPROVE THE USE OF ABBREVIATION TECHNIQUES IN SIMULTANEOUS INTERPRETING

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ABSTRACT

This article presented a modern view of various aspects of the study of simultaneous translation technologies. Technical issues were discussed in detail - innovative equipment for simultaneous translation. Performing simultaneous translation involves the use of an appropriate set of technical means. The translator must know this equipment and be able to use it, since the conditions of his work and the conditions for the perception of the translation by the audience depend on this. The work used materials from the websites of translation companies and bureaus providing simultaneous translation services, as well as electronic resources containing information about video remote and machine translation.

Key words: *simultaneous interpretation, consecutive interpretation, video remote interpretation.*

INTRODUCTION

The relevance of research. Today, in times of technological progress and globalization, people still, if not more, need translation of documents, oral communication at business meetings and various conferences. In translation practice, written and oral translation are distinguished. The work of any translator includes familiarization with this topic, working with a dictionary, compiling a glossary and constantly striving to keep abreast of political events. However, the work of an interpreter cannot be compared with the translation activity of a person who translates

in written form. For oral, especially simultaneous, translation, the most typical thing is the lack of time to think about it. In conditions of a general acceleration of the pace of life, this problem is increasingly critical. A more detailed study of the thought processes, often subconscious, involved in oral consecutive and simultaneous interpreting is required to maintain and improve the quality of interpreting.

Purpose of the study. Based on the relevance, in order to stimulate the successful development of the thought process and improve the quality of the interpreter's work in preparation for political events and during translation at them, the purpose of the study is to identify the correlation between the choice of interpretation strategy by the translator and the type of event in which the translator participates.

Taking into account the goal, we highlight the tasks of this research work:

1. Define the concepts of "translation strategy", "political event", "factors for choosing a translation strategy".
2. Familiarize yourself with the classifications of the above-mentioned terms and term combinations.
3. Analyze the influence of various conditions of the communicative situation of the event as factors on the translator's choice of translation strategy.

The theoretical significance of this article lies in the in-depth coverage of the issue of deducing spontaneous and intuitive thought processes occurring in the mind of an interpreter during the preparation and implementation of oral translation. This study contributes to the creation of a stimulus for the development of a knowledge base in the field of translation strategies research. In addition, some new aspects of the study of the problem of applying translation strategies are revealed, namely the influence of the type of event on the choice of translation strategy.

The practical significance of the work lies in the fact that the collected material can be used in practical recommendations for interpreters in preparation for work, to build a certain working system, a strategy for working at political (business) events. Also, the article material can be used by a methodologist - an interpreting teacher - to set an educational goal when drawing up programs and conducting classes.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

In order to define the term “translation strategy”, it is necessary to first form a clear understanding of the concept of “strategy”. This term has unclear semantics. A.G. Vitrenko in his scientific article about “Translation Strategy” writes that this concept was “returned” from the military field of knowledge to the terminology of translation studies [1]. The proof can be provided by definitions from the explanatory dictionary of S.I. Ozhegova: “1. The science of warfare, the art of warfare. Theory of military strategy. 2. General plan for waging war and combat operations. Victorious village.”

On the other hand, it can be assumed that this term was borrowed by domestic translation scholars from the English language, since this word is used quite widely among English-speaking researchers. A.G. Vitrenko writes about a certain vagueness and semantic breadth of the term “strategy” in the English language. According to Ozhegov, in Russian this concept took the following form: “3. Peren. The art of leading social and political struggles, as well as the general art of planning leadership based on correct and far-reaching forecasts.”

Carrying out simultaneous translation involves the use of an appropriate set of technical means. The translator must be able to use the equipment, since the conditions of his work and the conditions for the perception of the translation by the audience depend on this. The operating principle of the simultaneous translation installation is as follows: the speaker’s speech is transmitted to the interpreter through headphones, the translator, in turn, speaks the translation into a microphone, from where it is broadcast to the listener [10].

The simultaneous interpreter is located in a special room equipped with soundproofing. In stationary conference rooms, this is a small room with a table with a remote control and two chairs for synchronized speakers. If the hall is small, then the interpretation booth is located above the level of the seats and is equipped with a window with a wide view, through which the interpreters can see the speaker and the

hall. In large halls, a television monitor is installed on the table of synchronized interpreters, in which the speaker is visible [6].

In rooms temporarily used for simultaneous translation, a booth with a window or, as translators say, a “booth” (from the English “booth”) There are usually several such booths depending on the number of working languages of the congress or conference. The name of the cabin is determined by the language in which its translators work, for example, “Russian cabin” provides reproduction of the translation of the meeting into Russian,

“French cabin” – in French, etc. [4]. The simultaneous interpretation booth is designed for two people: one of them translates, the second listens to the translation and helps the first, for example, writes numbers, titles, surnames for him [6].

The cabin equipment consists of soundproof headphones, a microphone and a control panel [15]. Many synchronized speakers prefer to wear only one earphone to better monitor their voice and the speaker’s voice. The interpreter turns his own microphone on and off, which allows him to consult or talking to a colleague while working [4].

You should not place the microphone too close to your mouth, as individual sounds may become louder, which will be uncomfortable for listeners. It is recommended to work with a medium volume level of the incoming signal in order to hear your own translation and monitor your voice [5].

Two pairs of headphones are connected to the simultaneous translation console; sometimes they have a built-in microphone. On the remote control there is a microphone switch (right-left microphone), two microphone activation buttons and two volume controls (for each pair of headphones), as well as a channel switch for different languages, for example, channel 1 - Russian, channel 2 - English [6].

In addition, the control panel may have alarm buttons for communication with the speaker. Using these buttons, the interpreter can light up light signals in front of the speaker: “speak into the microphone”, “speak louder”.

In recent years, the so-called radio version of the installation for simultaneous interpretation, using ultrashort range radio waves, has become widespread. In this case, conference participants receive headphones or a headset with a translation language switch and volume control [8]. This allows the conference participant to listen to the presentation while moving around the room or even going out into the foyer.

With the advent of new technologies, it became possible to transmit video over the Internet, thanks to which the video remote translation service began to develop.

VRI (video remote interpreting) is a method of providing interpretation services using web cameras or cameras built into mobile devices. As a rule, in a situation of video remote interpretation, the communication participants are in the same room and interact with the translator using a computer or other device with Internet access and a video camera. Video remote interpretation provides the opportunity to receive professional interpretation in one of two modes: video call mode and video conference mode, when the conference participant sees a partner and an interpreter on the same screen [3].

No special equipment is required to use VRI. Often, Skype becomes the platform for video remote interpretation as the most common and accessible program with a video communication function. Many companies that provide VRI services create their own apps that allow you to directly connect with available translators. There are similar applications on the Russian translation market - for example, Cloud Interpreter. Translation companies and organizations, including government agencies, can use this platform to organize communication using it. The platform is developed for Android and iOS, that is, the translator can be accessed in video mode on a smartphone and tablet [2].

Conducting negotiations by phone or via Skype with the participation of an interpreter is one of the current ways to organize business contacts at a distance. Phone calls or online messengers have long proven themselves to be convenient and effective for establishing business connections. A conference call allows you to

discuss important aspects of your business in real time. At the same time, the simultaneous interpreter ensures the accuracy of understanding between the parties [11].

One of the means of improving the quality of translation activities is the automation of the translation process, which until recently was mainly solved within the framework of the translation of written texts [7]. Machine interpreting is a relatively new development that combines two technologies: machine translation and voice recognition software, in which automated software translates text from one language to another. It should be noted that similar technologies already exist, for example, the famous Siri application developed for iOS. The app uses natural speech processing to answer questions and make recommendations. Perhaps in the future, this application will be able to be used by every iPhone owner during an international conference [12], because today “Siri” supports 21 languages, including English, Arabic,

However, the main disadvantage of voice recognition software is that the program starts translating and converting the speaker’s speech as soon as it hears the first words. Developers face a difficult challenge: they must upgrade the technology so that it can predict and translate the speaker’s speech before he finishes speaking. To do this, developers need to turn attention to the grammatical features of languages, for example, in the case of languages where the verb is placed at the end of the sentence - German, Turkish, etc.

In one of his books, “The Age of Spiritual Machines,” Ray Kurzweil, a futurist and expert in the field of artificial intelligence, predicted that by 2029 computers will reach the level of live translation. “Of course, it [the computer] is far from the level of a human translator, but it will translate ordinary conversation and business negotiations quite tolerably,” notes Ray Kurzweil [9].

In 2005, Alex Waibel, director of the Center for Advanced Communication Technologies (interACT), pioneered research into machine simultaneous translation by creating a special device for speech recognition using electrodes. InterACT is a

joint venture between the German University of Karlsruhe (Universität Karlsruhe) and the American University of Carnegie Mellon (CMU).

During a teleconference between the two universities, Carnegie Mellon graduate student Stan Jou spoke quietly in Chinese while everyone at the conference heard him speak English. The device, which synchronously (with a slight lag of a few seconds) translated Wall Jow, perceived not sound, but muscle movements using

11 electrodes glued to the face and neck of a graduate student. Using these signals, the computer translated Chinese words into English and output synthesized speech through a speaker. During the demonstration, there were some inaccuracies in translation, when the machine confused two words with similar sounds [13].

Thus, by exploring new technologies for machine interpreting, you can conclude that the outcome of such technologies is still unpredictable. This method is quite unreliable, since computer programs do not take into account all the features of the language. In addition, it should be noted that speech recognition systems may be inaccurate and even useless when it comes to accents and dialects, extraneous noise and the slightest error in pronunciation. Unlike written language, human speech is unpredictable, and modern technologies, despite the development of artificial intelligence, still lack the human intuition and thinking to ensure full recognition of human speech.

CONCLUSION

The translator's task is to coordinate the parties and provide the opportunity to achieve joint decisions, plans and actions. When starting to translate business or political negotiations, the translator must take into account the personal qualities and values of both parties, be able to look at the problem through the eyes of the participants and formulate the translation taking into account the cultural characteristics of the country [21].

For example, French partners tend to conduct business negotiations much more lively than their foreign counterparts. They may interrupt another participant in communication to express their disagreement and provide counterarguments. In such

a situation, the translator should choose those translation strategies that will not “slow down” the progress of the discussion. There are situations when the translator is not sure or simply does not know the meaning of the word, so he has to resort to the strategy of sign translation [22, p. 223].

Telephone conversations also have their own characteristics. Participants in most cases try to allocate less time for such discussions. In this regard, the original messages are sometimes formulated illogically and chaotically, and redundant information appears. Thus, the problem of the lack of logical stress appears. To smooth out this situation, the translator uses strategies of waiting, maintaining linearity, and probabilistic forecasting.

Also, to identify a macro strategy, the situation is taken into account completely. If the translator knows the topic of the event in advance, he, as a rule, compiles a glossary on it, studies current figures in a particular field, etc. If there is a little more time for translation, the translator resorts to the trial and error strategy, since he has the resource to find the optimal translation option for a given topic [23].

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